

REVIEW PAPER

EVALUATION OF THE EMOTIONAL STATE IN THE OUTDOOR RECREATIONAL ACTIVITIES

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Abstract

The aim of the study is to evaluate the emotional state of volunteer participants in outdoor recreational activities (downhill skiing, cycling) by analysing their facial expressions and self-assessments of emotional state before and after the outdoor recreational activities. Twenty-four volunteers (8 women and 16 men with the average age of 38 years old) participated in the study. The emotional state of the participants was assessed by using Sports Emotion Questionnaire (SEQ) and a software "Face Reader 3.0." The data obtained in the study were processed using SPSS software. Spearman's rank correlation coefficient was calculated. The data obtained from the study shows that all the emotions of the participants are more intense before the recreational activities than after. Summarizing the findings obtained from the study, the results indicate the significance of using the Sports Emotion Questionnaire before and after recreational activities. As data received from self-assessments of emotional state often differ from data obtained by observation or by Face Reader, the recreational specialist needs to develop the ability to observe the emotional state of the respondents by using different methods. An interview or conversation is recommended before, during, and after the recreational activity. The information on the emotional state would allow adapting recreational activities to the current needs of the participant, encouraging more efficient involvement in the physical recreational process.

Keywords: *Recreational activities, emotional state, Face Reader, Sports Emotion Questionnaire*

Introduction

Recreational activity is a voluntary activity or experience that includes games or other activities in an individual's free time for the purpose of pleasure, physical and mental, and emotional well-being (Veal, 2011). Some of the sources describe the recreational as a mentally and physically healing activity (McLean et al., 2008). Participation in recreational activities not only prevents disease and improves physical health, but also benefits their stress and emotions (Asztalos et al., 2009). According to Ilhespy (2009), students' involvement in the outdoor recreational program is important to improve their self-confidence, positive thinking, and more perfectness. Outdoor recreational has been proven useful in promoting academic achievement, work commitment, critical thinking and in preventing delinquency. Based on international research conducted by Garst, Schneider, and Baker (2001), which studied the adolescents who participated in outdoor recreational activities, they found that the individuals had a positive impact on their perception and emotions while participating in outdoors activities.

The term "emotions" refers to any subjective experiences of a personality. When basic emotions or basic effects come together, complex emotional states arise. For example, anxiety, which includes fear, anger, guilt, shame, interest, agitation (Ekman, Davidson, 1994) The term emotional includes assessments of emotional states such as anxiety, stress, tension, depression, anger, confusion, embarrassment, energy, vigour, fatigue, positive affect, negative affect, optimism (Netz et al., 2005). Recognition of other people's emotions is mainly based on the external expression of emotions: facial expressions and postures, changes in speech, and changes in voice, behaviour. The first facial action coding system (FACS) was developed by Ekman and Friesen in 1978 based on facial anatomy. A system has developed those measures and describes facial behavior. Over time, this system has become the standard for coding facial expressions (Kuilenburg, Wiering & Uyl, 2005). Today technologies offer automatic facial expressions. Zaman and Shrimptom-Smith (2006), acknowledge that a great deal of information comes from facial expressions, but this information can be different from gestures and verbal expression of emotions. *Face Reader* is the program designed for automatic analysis of facial expressions (expression) and it is usually combined with other methods to give context and content to the data obtained.

The Sports Emotion Questionnaire (SEQ) measures a person's emotional state in relation to a specific event using the athlete's self-assessment of the emotional state after the event. The self-assessment survey measures the respondent's subjective opinion, self-interpretation of

the emotional state provides information about the subjective component of emotions or emotional experience (Zaman, Shrimpton-Smith, 2006). Based on the assumption that emotions are the answer to an event - the question of the expected, existing, or already happened questionnaire is formulated not on how the respondent feels in general, but in relation to a specific event (Jones & Lane, 2005). The emotional state plays an important role in physical activity because how a person feels during or after physical activity will largely determine his desire to engage in further activities (Biddle & Mutrie, 2005). Studies have also shown the effects of emotions on athletes before and during physical activity (Terry, 2011). Recognition of emotions in recreational allows for the possibility that changes in the emotional state will be observed in time and, if necessary, the emotional state will be regulated. Due to the many different emotions that a person can experience, it is not possible for the observer to observe and measure them all. It is most important and effective to measure emotions now of their experience because it is difficult to recall the exact same reactions to an event that took place, probably only a few minutes before, and which followed other events (Zaman, & Shrimpton-Smith, 2006). Also during recreational activities, it is often difficult to objectively assess whether the physical recreational activities performed have a positive or negative effect and have achieved the expected result because the athlete is moving and sometimes the conversation is not possible and how people feel during and after activity recreational activities may be critical in determining whether people engage in such activities in the future (Baglin et al., 2004, Biddle & Mutrie, 2005, Terry, 2011). Therefore, it is important to clarify when and under what conditions, recreational activities affect in a positive and a negative way on humans (athletes) emotional state. So, the aim of the study is to evaluate the emotional state through facial expressions and using the respondents' self-assessment of emotional state in downhill skier and cyclist before and after outdoor recreational activities.

Materials and methods

For the assessment of the emotional state the volunteer participants (8 women and 16 men with the average age of 38 years old) took part in the outdoor recreational activities (downhill ski and cycling). The Sport Emotion Questionnaire and the „Face Reader 3.0” software was used before and after these outdoor recreational activities.

Instruments. The Sport Emotion Questionnaire (Jones et al., 2005) consists of a five-factor model that covers a range of pleasant and unpleasant emotions that are experienced in competition and sports. It measures an athlete's feelings about their expected physical activity on five

scales: anxiety, depression, anger, anxiety, happiness. It can be used to assess the emotional state in various sports and physical activity-related events, including during and after the activity.

The “Face Reader 3.0” identifies 6 basic emotions: happy, angry, sad, surprised, scared, disgusted, as well as a neutral emotional state. The program captures facial expressions and determines a person's age, gender, ethnic identity, as well as identifies the subject (Zaman & Shrimpton-Smith, 2006).

Statistical Analysis The data obtained during the study were processed using SPSS software. Spearman`s rank correlation coefficient was calculated to find out whether statistically significant differences exist between the results of both - before and after recreational activities.

Results

The approach was developed and approbated in practice to evaluate downhill skier and cyclist emotional state before and after recreational activities. Several practical recommendations were created for recreational specialists. To detects the emotional state before recreational activity the SEQ was using. The gained data using SEQ show that respondents have emotional states related to happiness (41%) and excitement (39%) about the recreational activity in which they are going to participate. Some respondents feel anxious (19%), dejection (1%). None of the respondents showed anger. Comparing data between the genders it is observed that anxiety rates of women are higher than those of men, which coincides with the data obtained in the literature analysis. Anxiety is usually associated with anxiety and fear before acting responsibly, the outcome of which is uncertain. In this study, it is not possible to statistically prove that female anxiety rates are higher due to the small number of female respondents. (Fig.1)

Figure 1. Emotional state using SEQ before recreational activities (men and women)

Women, unlike men, experience less happiness and anxiety in connection with recreational activities, although these indicators are as similar as men's. The obtained data show that the women, unlike men, did not feel completely depressed and angry before the event.

To detect the emotional state after the recreational activities the "Face Reader 3.0." was used. The obtained data show that the respondents most often felt neutral emotions (23%) or happiness (21%) after recreational activities (Figure 2). These emotions are followed by sorrow, anger, etc. emotions not classified in Face Reader. Surprise, fear, and disgust also were detected. The respondents did not mention negative emotions in their emotional self-esteem reports, which coincides with the data in the theory that people tend to hide their negative experiences. The high percentage of neutral emotions felt could also indicate that respondents have used emotional displays - managing their feelings in a publicly acceptable form.

Figure 2. Emotional state after recreational activities (Using software "Face Reader 3.0.")

Figure 2 reflect the average distribution of average emotions, but there are large individual differences in the data, which leads to the conclusion that the emotional states of the respondents are different after the recreational al activity.

Comparing the obtained data between men and women, it can be concluded that men most often felt neutral emotions, followed by feelings of happiness, sadness, and other emotions. Women, on the other hand, felt the most controversial emotions - happiness and sadness, followed by neutral emotions (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Emotional state after recreational activities men and women (Using software “Face Reader 3.0.”)

Statistical analysis of the data was performed using the Spearman rank correlation coefficient to determine the interdependence of the traits. Further, the data were corrected to exclude the variables “neutral” and “other” because they are not comparable to other research methods and do not give an idea of the respondent's range of emotions. The obtained results show that happiness is statistically significantly correlated negatively with anger ($p < 0.05$) and dejection or sadness ($p < 0.05$). This means that respondents who show a higher sense of happiness than average show a lower-than-average sense of anger and dejection or sadness. Anger is statistically significantly correlated negatively with happiness ($p < 0.05$). This means that individuals who show a higher-than-average sense of anger show a lower-than-average sense of happiness. Dejection or sadness is statistically significantly correlated negatively with the feeling of happiness ($p < 0.05$). Individuals who show a higher-than-average feeling of dejection or sadness show a lower-than-average feeling of happiness.

Discussion

For a recreational activity to achieve its purpose, the persons performing physical activities must have appropriate personal abilities and skills. Otherwise, the result will be boredom (low challenge/high skill) or anxiety (high challenge/weak skill) (Biddle & Mutrie, 2005). Anxiety is usually associated with anxiety and fear before acting responsibly, the outcome of which one is not sure about. Participation in sports activities provides a positive experience for many people, however, research is mainly focused on the negative emotions of sports participants and their regulation. Positive emotions associated with sports are happiness and joy. Anxiety is generally considered to be a positive emotion associated with agitation and

activation of the autonomic nervous system. A person has positive expectations about their ability to achieve goals in a particular situation (Jones & Lane, 2005).

In the process of assessing the emotional state, it is important to consider the recreational person's previous experience in connection with recreational activity - both the length of service in recreational activities and the previous emotional experience in such activities. The low rates of dejection and anger are probably explained by the principle of volunteering in recreational – people who experience negative emotions relating with recreation activities are more likely to choose not to participate, thus avoiding potentially negative experiences and emotions.

The Sports Emotion Questionnaire (SEQ) is intended to assess the emotional state, but it does not provide information on the causes, context, and content of the emotional state. With this questionnaire it is possible to get an idea, mainly about the indicators of emotional well-being. SEQ focuses on the respondent's self- assessment of subjective feelings. The advantages of the Sports Emotion Questionnaire - the method is simple to use, quick to fill in, easy to process.

Conclusion

Analysing the negative emotions mentioned, observed, or obtained by the methodologies used in the study, it can be concluded that the respondents felt anxious, in some cases also anger and dejection or sadness before recreational activity. The negative emotions recorded after recreational activity were anger, sorrow, and disgust. A more detailed study of these emotions could explain the reasons for the occurrence of these emotions. For example, anxiety is characteristic of a person before a responsible action or event, the success of which he or she is not sure about. Sadness involves loss or separation from something valuable. Sadness can be caused by loss, illness, etc., which means the loss of a source of well-being and joy. Anger is caused by frustration or overwhelming shame and ashamed, an individual is aware only of those traits that at the time seem ugly or inadequate to him (Jones, 2003).

Using mathematical statistical methods, the data obtained by the Sports Emotions Questionnaire before recreational activities and the data obtained by the “Face Reader 3.0.” software after recreational activity was compared. Happiness and anxiety prevail before recreational activities, while happiness and sad predominate after recreational, as these emotions show the highest arithmetic mean values.

Summarizing the findings obtained from the study, the results indicate the significance of using the Sports Emotion Questionnaire before

and after recreational activities. As data received from self-assessments of emotional state often differ from data obtained by observation or by Face Reader, the recreational specialist needs to develop the ability to observe the emotional state of the respondents by using different methods. An interview or conversation is recommended before, during, and after the recreational activity. The information on the emotional state would allow adapting recreational activities to the current needs of the participant, encouraging more efficient involvement in the physical recreational process.

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